

Optoelectronic perovskite film characterization via machine vision

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Abstract

We present our research for fast and reliable extraction of bandgap and absorption quality values for triple-cation perovskite thin films from sample scans. Our approach leverages machine learning methods, namely convolutional neural networks, to perform regression tasks aimed at predicting the properties of interest. To this end, thin film samples were synthesized via blade-coating and their photoluminescence and ultraviolet–visible spectra collected, along with the film thickness. We propose a method of computing a dimensionless figure of merit we called the Area Under Absorption Coefficient (AUAC), its purpose being to qualitatively evaluate the absorption quality of perovskite films for use in photovoltaic modules. This work demonstrates the usability of simple imaging techniques to analyze experimental samples while requiring only a feasibly acquirable initial amount of data. Our reported method can help speed up time consuming material optimizations by reducing lab time spent on recurrent characterization, nicely synergizes with high throughput production lines and could be adapted for quick extraction of other optoelectrical quantities.

Keywords

Machine learning; Perovskite; Blade coating; Property extraction; Thin films

1 **OPTOELECTRONIC PEROVSKITE FILM CHARACTERIZATION**
2 **VIA MACHINE VISION**

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Abstract. We present our research for fast and reliable extraction of bandgap and absorption quality values for triple-cation perovskite thin films from sample scans. Our approach leverages machine learning methods, namely convolutional neural networks, to perform regression tasks aimed at predicting the properties of interest. To this end, thin film samples were synthesized via blade-coating and their photoluminescence and ultraviolet-visible spectra collected, along with the film thickness. We propose a method of computing a dimensionless figure of merit we called the Area Under Absorption Coefficient (AUAC), its purpose being to qualitatively evaluate the absorption quality of perovskite films for use in photovoltaic modules. This work demonstrates the usability of simple imaging techniques to analyze experimental samples while requiring only a feasibly acquirable initial amount of data. Our reported method can help speed up time consuming material optimizations by reducing lab time spent on recurrent characterization, nicely synergizes with high throughput production lines and could be adapted for quick extraction of other optoelectrical quantities.

5 Machine Learning, Perovskite, Blade Coating, Property Extraction, Thin Films

6 **1. Introduction**

7 The need for accelerated optimization of energy conversion technologies arises
8 with rising energy demands and the ever present problem of climate change [1]. Per-
9 ovskite solar cells have shown promise in research, due to their versatile bandgap
10 tuning properties, high absorption coefficient, ambipolar charge transport, large
11 charge carriers lifetime/diffusion length and power up to those of silicon solar cells
12 [2–7]. The scientific community has clearly taken an interest, as illustrated by
13 the steeply rising number of publications on the subject since 2013 [8]. However,
14 adapting module device deposition processes and material compositions optimized
15 for small area devices to large scale device production for commercial use is one of
16 the most challenging aspects for perovskite technology exploitation [9, 10]. Since

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17 the polycrystalline nature of solution-processed perovskite layers induces defects,
18 such as at grain boundaries and vacancies during the fabrication process [11], the
19 main issue is finding optimized up-scalable processes to minimize losses and to
20 reduce material waste [12, 13]. A detailed understanding of the perovskite film
21 formation mechanisms by adopting scalable coating techniques can drive the tech-
22 nology out of the laboratory.

23 Most discoveries in materials science have been achieved using empirical methods
24 [14], which consume a rather high amount of resources. Such resources include
25 man power, materials cost and energy consumption by lab equipment. Each of
26 these quantities is limited in practice, and in some cases may be limited by addi-
27 tional factors. An example of this would be the use of toxic compounds, restricting
28 the amount of time a lab researcher can safely work in the lab [15]. As the possible
29 configuration space of scalable deposition techniques, used materials and fabrica-
30 tion parameters is vast, empiric methods of optimization seem infeasibly slow. The
31 emergence of machine learning (ML) techniques for use in materials science may
32 open up pathways to more resource-efficient experimentation, and therefore aid in
33 alleviating the up-scaling issue of perovskite based solar cells in a smaller time-
34 frame [16, 17]. One such pathway is the use of sample images, either generated by
35 imaging techniques, simple photographs or optical scans, along with a measured
36 physical property to train a ML network. Theoretically, all properties that are of
37 an optical nature or related to optical phenomena can be used in this approach,
38 as the sample images provide optical information for the algorithm to interpret.
39 Schubert *et al.* have provided an overview of spatially resolved imaging methods
40 for perovskite solar cell analysis, all of which can in theory serve as possible model
41 inputs [18]. With sufficient amounts of data, a model may be created that can pre-
42 dict the property of interest specific to the research question from a suitable image
43 alone, as already demonstrated in multiple publications [19–22]. For repeated syn-
44 thesis of one perovskite type using the same fabrication technique, this results in a
45 substantially lower amount of experimental resources used while trying to achieve
46 results which are consistent concerning the properties of interest. The characteri-
47 zation time is expected to decrease from an order of hours to an order of minutes
48 in terms of time, as well as requiring only the electricity needed to run the trained
49 algorithm for the property prediction instead of using lab resources, which should
50 generally have a higher use of electricity. An example would be the prediction
51 of the materials bandgap (BG) or an objective function evaluating the absorption
52 quality by simply optically scanning a sample with a document scanner and pass-
53 ing the resulting image through a pre-trained image processing network. In that
54 case, an image created by a simple document scanner would yield similar applica-
55 tion specific information as a resource-intensive optoelectronic measurement such
56 as a photoluminescence (PL) or Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy. It has
57 to be stressed here that the model predictions are by nature less accurate than the
58 measurements, but should give sufficient indication where the applied fabrication
59 parameters yield consistent results or deviate strongly. The advantage and novelty
60 of this work lies in the simplicity of data acquisition and model structuring, which
61 implies that very basic imaging techniques and model architectures are sufficient
62 for training a network to quantify elementary optoelectronic properties.
63 In the following, we present our recent work on ML networks for prediction of

64 both bandgap and absorption quality from sample scans. The samples were fabri-
 65 cated from precursors using a blade-coating approach in ambient air, yielding triple
 66 cation perovskite thin-films. We constructed a convolutional neural network archi-
 67 tecture suitable for evaluating both properties of interest, which yielded models
 68 with a mean test set prediction error of 8.3 % mean absolute percentage error at
 69 maximum. This performance is comparable to that of previously published models
 70 created to achieve similar tasks, even though the comparison is impeded by the
 71 inconsistent performance criteria used across ML literature. A NRMSE of 20 % for
 72 a similar model correlating dark field microscopy images to the electrical conduc-
 73 tance was reported by Srivastava *et al.* [19] and an accuracy of 95.28 % was reached
 74 in a model published by Taherimaksousi *et al.* [20]. Said model was designed to
 75 classify sample photograph areas as covered, partially covered or uncovered.
 76 Our results imply that the desired correlations are not only trainable, but also
 77 quite precise with only 66 data entries contained in the dataset so far.

78 2. Results

79 **2.1. Experimental sample preparation and characterization.** In this work,
 80 we deposited the triple cation perovskite by adopting the procedure developed
 81 in a recent publication on a substrate size comparable to a mini-module (5.6 x
 82 9 cm²) [23]. An overview of the deposition process flow and the raw data collection
 83 procedure can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Deposition process flow and raw data collection from the perovskite-coated substrate

84 The perovskite (PVSK) solution and the antisolvent isopropanol (IPA) were
 85 deposited sequentially by the blade coating technique assisted by hot air blowing.

86 In the first step, the air assistance is necessary to pre-dry the layer and smooth
87 the surface, while it quickly dries the solvent in the second step.

88 Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) trapping during the film formation is an open issue,
89 because it formed voids at the PVSK-substrate interface [24].

90 IPA removes the DMSO excess and helps the crystallization of the perovskite,
91 because it has a lower boiling point and higher viscosity in respect to DMSO [25].
92 The presence of solvents with high boiling points produces PbI_2 precipitation during
93 the perovskite crystal nucleation causing an incomplete layer conversion. [26]

94 Finally, the substrate was annealed at 100°C for 40 min to permit perovskite
95 growth [27].

96 The entire process was performed in a controlled environment (25°C , 30% RH)
97 by using a semi-automatic blade-coating machine (Cicci Research Srl) equipped
98 with a heated moving table, a blade-coater and a hot-air blower [23, 28, 29]. The
99 process is completely confined inside the machine’s box with controlled temperature
100 and humidity.

101 The moving plate speed, the flow rate and the air temperature were variably set
102 by the machine’s software, while the material volume of $70\ \mu\text{l}$, the blade-substrate
103 gap of $500\ \mu\text{m}$ in the first and $300\ \mu\text{m}$ in the second step were kept constant. The
104 raw data for the preparation of the dataset were gathered by changing the speed
105 (from 5 to 50 mm/sec), the air flux (from 0 to 250 l/min) and temperature (from
106 130 to 330°C) related to the perovskite and the antisolvent deposition. After ther-
107 mal annealing, the 70 perovskite-coated layers were scanned from the front and
108 back side (i.e. the glass side of the substrate), as can be seen in Figure 1. UV-Vis
109 and PL spectra, as well as profile thicknesses of the layer were collected from three
110 control spots (two in case of PL) on each perovskite-coated substrate. The location
111 of the control spots can be identified using Figure 1.

112 While checking the database, a total of four samples had to be discarded. Two
113 of them showed insufficient film coverage on the control spots, one had a barely
114 identifiable PL peak and the UV-Vis spectrum of another sample did not cover the
115 entirety of the usual wavelength range. The final database therefore contained 66
116 samples, with each sample being characterized by 2 optical scans, 2 PL measure-
117 ments, 3 UV-Vis measurements and 3 thickness measurements. The quality of the
118 films varied in terms of coverage and defects, which is beneficial in the construction
119 of an ML model as the diversity of data helps in creating a more generalizable
120 algorithm. Further removal of samples would deprive the algorithm of information
121 about common defects on still viable cells.

122 An example of a scan pair after cropping can be found in Figure 2, additional
123 examples are provided in Figure S3 in the supporting information.

124 **2.2. Machine Learning architecture construction.** A convolutional neural
125 network (CNN) architecture was constructed in python using tensorflow [30]. This
126 network type was chosen due to it having been specifically designed to handle image
127 recognition tasks [31, 32]. The CNN was constructed in a way that takes a scan pair
128 as input. The scans taken from the front and the back of the sample are handled in
129 separate wings of the model at first. Each wing is comprised of a convolution layer,
130 a max pooling layer, two more convolution layers, another max pooling layer and
131 a final convolution layer. Before passing on the information, it is reformatted to a
132 vector using a flattening layer and computed down to a size of 10 using two dense
133 layers. The input pictures are colored and therefore possess three color channels,

Figure 2. Examples of cropped sample scans taken from a) the front and b) the back

134 which are computed down to a single channel in the first convolution layer. The two
135 vectors output by the CNN wings are consequently concatenated and the resulting
136 vector of size 20 is passed through three more dense layers to arrive at a single
137 output needed for the intended regression tasks. A lambda layer was used right
138 before the output layer to shift the normalized targets upwards in order to enable
139 the usage of a more intuitive loss function and increase the networks sensitivity in
140 a region where it exhibited generally worse performance. More information con-
141 cerning the hyperparameters used in the architecture can be found in Section 4.8.
142 The basic model architecture remained the same for all applications in this work,
143 only the input sizes had to be changed in accordance with the subtype of model,
144 an overview of which can be found in Table 1. Which subtype of the algorithm was
145 chosen depended on the targeted physical property and whether this property was
146 averaged. A schematic of the model architecture blocks can be found in Figure 3.
147 A more detailed version of the model architecture is provided in Figure S4 in the
148 supporting information.

149 **2.3. Optical scan based bandgap prediction.** The CNN model outlined above
150 was first used to predict bandgap (BG) values from the scans. Those were extracted
151 from the PL measurements by locating the wavelength with the highest intensity in
152 the emission range. For a single direct band gap semiconductor, the PL spectrum
153 will show a single, well-pronounced peak in the emission range. The center of this

Figure 3. A schematic of the basic model architecture

154 peak corresponds to the most likely emission wavelength, and therefore approxi-
 155 mates the bandgap [33]. While the wavelength with the highest intensity in the
 156 emission range does not necessarily correspond to the center of the peak, it provides
 157 a reasonable estimation. Other influencing factors were either kept consistent, such
 158 as the temperature or pressure, or stem from the crystal quality. Since the crystal
 159 quality needs to be reasonably consistently synthesizable for device manufacturing,
 160 detecting deviations in the extracted bandgap also detects deviations in crystal
 161 quality. In addition, the method would likely be applicable for more sophisticated
 162 bandgap extraction protocols, such as the one outlined by Makula *et al.* [34]. The
 163 bandgap values have been normalized between 0 and 1 using a min-max normal-
 164 ization approach to fit with the chosen tanh activation function in the layer before
 165 the lambda layer and to ensure the correct operation of the ReLu activations [35].

166 After normalization, the values were shifted up by 1 to fit with the model archi-
 167 tecture. An overview of the emission peak shapes is provided in Figure S1 in the
 168 supporting information.

169

170 We trained two different subtypes of the basic architecture for this target prop-
 171 erty. The subtypes differ in the way the data preprocessing is handled: Model A
 172 keeps the size of the scans intact, relating the complete images to the averaged
 173 bandgap value acquired by computing the arithmetic mean between the bandgaps
 174 extracted from the two control points where PL measurements were taken. In con-
 175 trast, model B utilizes picture halves and correlates them to the extracted bandgap
 176 values from the control points located in the scan fragment. Therefore, Model A
 177 has less precisely calculated targets and less samples, but more information for the

178 algorithm to interpret per image, while Model B has more samples and more exact
179 targets to work with, but only half as much information contained in each image.

180 Both models were designed to utilize augmented data, which were generated by
181 the process detailed in Section 4.5 and broadly used techniques surveyed by Shorten
182 and Khoshgoftaar [36].

183 For reference, an overview over all constructed models is provided in Table 1.
184 The images were split using the image slicer package [37]. Data augmentation was
185 achieved by flipping the images along a horizontal axis, which was facilitated by
186 either the pillow or cv2 python package, for split or whole images, respectively [38,
187 39]. To match the doubled amount of input data, the target entries were doubled
188 as well, making sure the order of output entries fit with the inputs. The code was
189 structured in a way that made sure the scan segmentation was done before the
190 augmentation process, keeping the target value identical for both the original and
191 the flipped image. Before being used as inputs, all image data was normalized by
192 dividing the entire matrix by 255.

193 To evaluate model subtype performance, a regular model with a 95 to 5 training
194 set to test set split was trained for both subtypes. An evaluation graph, a test error
195 histogram and a linear regression graph on both test and training set predictions
196 were constructed from this regular model and can be found in Figures 4 and 5. The
197 evaluation graph maps the actual targets of the algorithm against its predictions,
198 so for an ideal model, all points should be located on the bisector line. The linear
199 regression of all points contained in the evaluation graph serves as an indication of
200 how well the algorithm could be trained overall.

201 All datapoints were used instead of only the testing set points, as the dataset
202 was too small to yield a sufficient amount for a meaningful linear regression. In
203 addition, a special case of KFold validation was used. The code was set up to train
204 as many models as there were data points, keeping a single datapoint for model
205 validation. By collecting all the single test predictions from this procedure, a graph
206 can be generated that gives insight into the representability of each point compared
207 to the rest of the dataset. The results for model A in the explained above form can
208 be found in Figure 4. It should be noted that all axes labeled with "Predictions"
209 are meant to be read as predictions made for the target property indicated on the
210 other axis.

211 The histograms show the percentage error, as defined by $100\%(P - I)/I$, with
212 P signifying the predictions of the model and I signifying the model input. The
213 averaged bandgaps ranged between 752.18 nm and 768.495 nm, so the normalization
214 can be inverted via the following formula:

$$\overline{v_{BG}} = (v_{norm}^A - 1) * 16.315 \text{ nm} + 752.18 \text{ nm}. \quad (1)$$

215 The evaluation graph shows good behavior, with all points being ordered around
216 the bisector line, indicating a close correlation between targets and predictions.

217 At the highest BG values, a small drop beneath the bisector line can be seen,
218 which is present in all results to a degree.

219 The upward shift of the normalization range by 1 helped mitigate this issue. The
220 test histogram shows errors between 0 and 17.5 %, with a mean of 8.3 % and a
221 standard deviation of 6.17 %. These values can be considered sufficient with regards
222 to the fairly limited amount of data and therefore small test set sizes. If both test
223 and training set predictions are fit using linear regression, a mean percentage error

Figure 4. Overview of performance results for Model type A, composed of a) evaluation graph, b) test histogram, c) linear regression of all predictions and d) KFold approach evaluation. All axes labeled "Predictions" refer to predictions of the property given on the corresponding axis in the same graph

224 of 2.23 % is achieved, with a very good R value and slope of 0.98 for both. The
 225 KFold evaluation graph shows a much larger spread, which was to be expected based
 226 on the properties of the method. Each model only uses a single datapoint as its test
 227 set, leading to deviations in proportion to the representability of that individual
 228 point. The R value of 0.73 illustrates the much less linear nature compared to the
 229 regular model. It is notable that the results deviate most at the two outer thirds
 230 of the range, with lower BG values being overestimated and higher ones being
 231 underestimated. The latter fact helps understand why a drop of predictions can be
 232 found at the upper border in the regular model, where the accuracy of the KFold
 233 seems especially low. Also of note are the pillar like structures such as at 1.0 of
 234 the KFold evaluation graph, which speak for the fact that the model differentiates
 235 sample scans by appearances. This appearance may deviate between samples due
 236 to differences in coverage or amount of defects, but the corresponding BG value
 237 might be the same, especially in the averaged case. These pillar like structures can
 238 also be found in the same spots of the regular model evaluation graph, albeit less
 239 visibly pronounced. The result graphs for model B can be found in Figure 5.

240 The measured bandgaps ranged between 750.46 nm and 772.21 nm, so the nor-
 241 malization can be inverted via the following formula:

Figure 5. Overview of performance results for Model type B, composed of a) evaluation graph, b) test histogram, c) linear regression of all predictions and d) KFold approach evaluation. All axes labeled "Predictions" refer to predictions of the property given on the corresponding axis in the same graph

$$v_{BG} = (v_{norm}^B - 1) * 21.75 \text{ nm} + 750.46 \text{ nm}. \quad (2)$$

242 The evaluation graph implies good performance for model B as well. The test
 243 histogram shows errors between 0 and 16 %, with a mean of 4.39 % and a standard
 244 deviation of 4.77 %, outperforming model A. The linear regression performed on
 245 the whole dataset indicated a very low mean percentage error of 1.13 %, which is
 246 almost half the error compared to model A. The R value of 0.99 is also superior to
 247 model A, while the slope is very slightly worse with 0.96 compared to 0.98. The
 248 KFold evaluation shows similar behavior to the model A KFold, with the highest
 249 representability being present near the graph center and very slightly better R
 250 value of 0.75. The outer regions are, once again, overestimated in the small and
 251 underestimated in the large regime, with visibly less accurate predictions in the
 252 latter regime. The pillar like structures are also present, especially at about 1.1
 253 and 1.7 normalized shifted BG. Model B overall seems to be superior to model A,
 254 which is most likely caused by the larger dataset generated by cutting images into
 255 halves while still retaining sufficient information per image to predict the target
 256 property.

257 **2.4. Optical scan based absorption quality evaluation.** The basic network
 258 architecture was also used to train models aiming at a target meant to qualitatively
 259 describe the absorption behavior of the film. To this end, the UV-Vis spectra and
 260 the film thicknesses gathered from measurements at the three control points were
 261 used. There are two common types of handling the absorbance measured via UV-
 262 Vis spectroscopy: Simple calculation of the absorption coefficient or employing an
 263 area-under-the-curve (AOC) approach. The first method calculates the absorption
 264 coefficient at a certain wavelength by dividing the absorbance with the sample
 265 thickness, as outlined by Renner [40].

266 With this method, the absorption capabilities at a certain wavelength can be
 267 computed. The second approach is the AOC approach, where the area under the
 268 UV-Vis curve is computed via integration, as outlined by Dagdu *et al.* [41]. This
 269 approach is used for quality control analysis in a pharmaceutical context by a
 270 majority of researchers [42, 43], albeit not as a figure of merit for absorption ca-
 271 pabilities, although its characteristics are clearly suited for this role. Additionally,
 272 in an ML context, both methods exhibit the problem of having units of m^{-1} or
 273 nm , respectively. If possible, a dimensionless figure of merit is preferred, since the
 274 network architecture has no prior information on the underlying physics if not ex-
 275 plicitly coded in. With this in mind, a combined approach was chosen: The UV-Vis
 276 measurements were scaled by the corresponding measured film thicknesses, and the
 277 area under the resulting curves was calculated using a Simpson’s rule of integration
 278 as implemented in the SciPy python package [44]. Since the initial curves were
 279 dimensionless, division by thickness yields a unit of nm^{-1} and subsequent integra-
 280 tion turns it dimensionless again. With this quantity, a qualitative categorization
 281 of the absorption capabilities across all measured wavelengths should be possible.
 282 For greater precision, the integration range is stopped at the band gap wavelength,
 283 as lower photon energies do not contribute to the potentially usable spectrum in
 284 photovoltaic devices. Since there were three UV-Vis measurements conducted per
 285 sample in contrast to only two PL measurements, the integration was stopped at
 286 the average of the two BG values, introducing slight inaccuracies. Because no
 287 mention of this approach could be found in literature, we named this constructed
 288 figure of merit the AUAC-number, where the abbreviation stands for Area Under
 289 Absorption Coefficient:

$$\text{AUAC} = \int_{\nu_{\text{ExpMin}}}^{\overline{\nu_{\text{BG}}}} A/d \, d\nu, \quad (3)$$

290 Where ν_{ExpMin} is the smallest experimentally measured wavelength, $\overline{\nu_{\text{BG}}}$ is the
 291 wavelength of the average bandgap, A is the absorbance and d is the thickness
 292 of the sample. A visual representation of the AUAC definition can be found in
 293 Figure S2 in the supporting information. The AUAC-numbers were normalized in
 294 the same fashion as the bandgap values. An overview of the UV-Vis spectra before
 295 any preprocessing has been applied can be found in Figure S1 in the supporting
 296 information.

297 With a qualitative figure of merit for the absorption quality, another two model
 298 subtypes were constructed in a similar fashion as before. Model C correlates the
 299 whole scan with the arithmetic mean of all AUAC-numbers generated from the three
 300 control points of one sample, analogously to model A with the bandgap. Model D
 301 uses thirds of scans and relates them to the AUAC-numbers from the individual

302 control points. Due to their similar concept, the same tradeoff between amount
 303 of samples, target calculation precision and information contained in each sample
 304 applies between models C and D as for models A and D. The same augmentation
 305 scheme as with the bandgap models has been used. Further information on these
 306 models can be found in Table 1.
 307 The evaluation graphs for models C, in the same shape as for the models before,
 308 can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Overview of performance results for Model type C, composed of a) evaluation graph, b) test histogram, c) linear regression of all predictions and d) KFold approach evaluation. All axes labeled "Predictions" refer to predictions of the property given on the corresponding axis in the same graph

309 The averaged AUAC-numbers ranged between 0.277 and 3.624, the inversion of
 310 the normalization is therefore given by

$$\overline{\text{AUAC}} = (\text{AUAC}_{\text{norm}} - 1) * 3.347 + 0.277. \quad (4)$$

311 When looking at the evaluation, it is noticeable right away that the majority
 312 of points are located slightly below the bisector line, rather than being distributed
 313 around it. With errors on the test set ranging from 0 to 16 %, with a mean of 7.77
 314 % and a standard deviation of 6.61 %, the performance is comparable to model A
 315 nonetheless. The linear regression on the whole dataset shows the same R value of
 316 0.98 for model C as for model A, with a slightly worse slope of 0.96. The regression
 317 line appears to be shifted downwards from the bisector line, however. The KFold

318 evaluations R value of 0.74 is comparable to the models before, the regions of over-
 319 and underestimation appear again as well. The model seems to perform the worst
 320 on the high end of the AUAC range, similarly to the BG models. These regions
 321 seem to be larger now, with the turning point being at 1.4. Overall, there seem
 322 to be slightly more points below the bisector line, and with greater distances to it
 323 than the points above said line. This might have contributed to the downshifted
 324 nature of the regular model performance. Some pillar like structures are present
 325 here in the KFold as well, such as at around 1.7.
 326 Finally, the results for model type D shall be examined. The graphs for this model
 327 type, in the familiar shape, can be found in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Overview of performance results for Model type D, composed of a) evaluation graph, b) test histogram, c) linear regression of all predictions and d) KFold approach evaluation. All axes labeled "Predictions" refer to predictions of the property given on the corresponding axis in the same graph

328 The AUAC-numbers ranged between 0.204 and 4.347, resulting a in a normal-
 329 ization inversion function of

$$\text{AUAC} = (\text{AUAC}_{\text{norm}}^{\text{D}} - 1) * 4.143 + 0.204. \quad (5)$$

330 The evaluation graph for model D suggests very good behavior, except for a
 331 single test set point at about 1.9. This point also affects the test set histogram
 332 heavily, turning an error range of 0 to about 14 % to one of 0 to 35 %. However,
 333 the mean test error of 8 % and standard deviation of 7.52 % are still comparable to

334 model C and model A. The linear regression on the whole dataset shows an R value
335 of 0.98 and a slope of 0.98, slightly outperforming model C and matching those
336 parameters for model A. The KFold evaluation shows the worst behavior so far,
337 with an R value of only 0.64. The same overall shape as in model C can be seen, but
338 there are a lot more points situated away from the bisector line. One of those points
339 can clearly be identified as the very badly performing test set point in the regular
340 model, which provides some insight into the bad behavior at that particular point.
341 The region of worst performance was the upper limit of the AUAC, in agreement
342 with all results before. In addition, the KFold contains more pillar like structures,
343 such as at about 1.45. While model B was in almost all aspects superior to model
344 A, model D seems to be no major improvement on model C. Splitting the inputs
345 into thirds might generate more datapoints, but for this application it also appears
346 to introduce additional problems in terms of dataset representability.
347 A general overview of all trained models in terms of type, size and type of input
348 data and target properties, training and evaluation loss as well as the number of
349 epochs the models were trained can be found in Table 1.

350

3. Discussion

351 This work provides proof that machine learning based quantification of optical
352 properties is possible even while using rather small sets of simple, easy to produce
353 scans. It also shows that the trained model is able to give quick predictions for
354 wanted physical properties with a tolerable margin of error of 8.3 % at maximum.
355 Since the model has been trained on perovskite thin films of one material using
356 a single deposition technique with different fabrication parameters, it has to be
357 noted that it cannot be expected to perform well for other perovskites or deposition
358 techniques.

359 However, the comparative ease of data acquisition makes the approach feasible
360 for problems where repeat fabrication and characterization of samples is a necessary
361 part of optimizing the deposition parameters. This might prove especially useful
362 for high-throughput production lines, where the state of the fabricated film can
363 be checked online [45]. Works by Sun *et al.* [46] and Du *et al.* [47] have already
364 illustrated the potential of online characterization, which is achieved by automated
365 measurement techniques. Insufficiently performant samples can be discarded with-
366 out having to pass through the entire fabrication cycle, or, with some assistance
367 from the realm of experiment guiding [48–50], the fabrication parameters could be
368 adjusted on the fly to potentially balance out inferior film quality of the sample
369 or layer fabricated before. By substituting the automated measurement techniques
370 with a trained ML model as described above, the characterizations can be done in
371 less time, increasing the sample yield of the process.

372 It should be stressed again that the bandgap extraction protocol from the PL
373 used in this work is of a simpler nature, and could be improved with additional
374 measurements. To that end, finding a tradeoff between bandgap precision and
375 additional resources spent to improve said precision would be of interest. The
376 AUAC serves as a numerical concept as of now, with its impact on actual solar cell
377 performance still unexplored. Further investigation into the correlation between
378 the AUAC of the perovskite layer and total device efficiency would be important to
379 gauge its usefulness outside its theoretical conception. However, these two target

Table 1. Table overview of the different model types, their inputs, their target properties, final training and evaluation losses and the numbers of epochs the models were trained

Model	Input data	Target property	Mean test loss	Whole set R value	KFold R value
A	132 picture pairs	132 averaged norm. shifted BGs	8.3 %	0.98	0.73
B	264 halved picture pairs	264 norm. shifted BGs	4.39 %	0.99	0.75
C	132 picture pairs	132 averaged norm. shifted AUAC-numbers	7.77 %	0.98	0.74
D	396 thirds of picture pairs	396 norm. shifted AUAC- numbers	8 %	0.98	0.64

380 values only represent a small sampling of the properties which could hypothetically
381 serve as the models targets.

382 As much of the optical properties of a material can potentially be extracted from
383 scans, photographs or images, and these properties are in turn linked to electrical
384 aspects, the limits of this method are as of now unexplored.

385 Further research in this direction might provide even better model performance
386 and gradually illuminate the full range of physical quantities which are extractable
387 by this approach. The method has already been shown to work for film coverage,
388 film thicknesses, bandgaps, absorption quality and conductance [19, 20, 22]. More
389 promising properties could be reflectance, transmittance, dispersion and the refrac-
390 tive index in terms of optics, defect density and defect types in terms of structural
391 properties and dielectric permittivity or polarizability in terms of electrical proper-
392 ties. The two electrical properties can be computed from optical quantities, which
393 might indicate that the needed information for prediction is contained inside sample
394 pictures [51].

395 In order to take full advantage of this work’s discovery, it might prove useful
396 in the future to scan or photograph fabricated films and devices alongside the up
397 to now standard characterization procedures. With a sufficiently large database at
398 hand, more models of the type described in this work may be trained. It would
399 be imperative to make sure the database is consistent, which is common practice
400 in the computational community [52, 53]. One approach to achieve consistency
401 is by abiding by the FAIR principle [54]. This might result in long term savings
402 of valuable resources, due to eliminating the need for replication of data already
403 measured by a different group of researchers. In addition, improved performance
404 of models trained on greater amounts of data can be expected as a consequence
405 of database cultivation. However, in the realm of ML, datasets with thousands
406 of entries or more are common [55–57]. Setting up databases of a similar size
407 would take a considerable amount of work, but could be worth the investment,
408 especially since valuable data is already being gathered through independent efforts
409 of multiple labs without the final step of properly sharing and comparing them in
410 a unified framework. The method is suited for most optimization problems that
411 rely on a grid search of the fabrication parameter space, as long as the information
412 needed for characterization is visible to the ML algorithm in the images.

413 In conclusion, the outlined method is promising for accelerating perovskite solar
414 cell research focussed on optimization of fabrication parameters of a particular
415 deposition method and reliant on recurrent synthesis of one particular perovskite.
416 Its full potential could be explored by gathering a larger database and replicating
417 the method with other properties to check for viability in the future, or by trying
418 to apply the method to a database consisting of another, singular material.

419

4. Methods

420 **4.1. Materials.** PbI_2 and PbBr_2 from TCI Co. Ltd was used along with CsI, For-
421 mamidinium iodide (FAI) and Methylammonium bromide (MABr) from Great Cell
422 Solar to synthesize $\text{Cs}_{0.05}(\text{MA}_{0.17}\text{FA}_{0.83})_{0.95}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.83}\text{Br}_{0.17})_3$ thin films according to
423 Vesce *et al.* [23]. The solvents used were Dimethylformamide (DMF) and Dimethyl
424 Sulfoxide (DMSO). The used antisolvent was isopropanol (IPA).

425 **4.2. Film fabrication.** The perovskite layer was deposited by a semi-automatic
426 blade-coating machine designed and developed by Cicci Research Srl and CHOSE.

427 The machine is composed by a motorized thermal vacuum plate, a blade head, a
428 hot/dry air blower, a pumping syringe and an IR lamp. The instrument operates
429 at controlled temperature and humidity conditions. The detailed film fabrication
430 procedure is reported by Vesce *et al.* [23].

431 **4.3. Characterization.** The film profiles are measured using a profilometer (DEK-
432 TAK 150, Veeco Instruments Inc.). The optical analysis is performed with a UV-
433 Vis spectrometer (UV-2550, Shimadzu) and with a PL measurement system (Arkeo,
434 Ciccì Research). PL spectra are collected with an aspheric lens with a 10 mm diam-
435 eter close to the substrate and recorded by a CCD based spectrometer. Integration
436 time and number of averaging are maintained the same to compare the results.
437 The substrate is fired with 45° inclination with a diode-pumped solid-state (DPSS)
438 Nd:YVO₄+KTP Laser (Peak wavelength 532 nm \pm 1 nm, Optical power 1 mW on
439 a circular spot of 2 mm of diameter: 31 mW/cm² or a collimated UV LED (Peak
440 wavelength 380 nm \pm 5 nm). The pictures of the depositions were acquired at 600
441 dpi resolution by scanner HP LaserJet Pro M148fdw.

442 **4.4. KFold validation.** The KFold algorithm performed in this work is a special
443 case of KFold validation. KFold validation evenly segments the dataset into a
444 number of k folds, then iteratively designates each fold as validation data and
445 the rest as corresponding training data [58]. In total a number of k models are
446 trained, which are then evaluated on their folds. The reasoning for performing
447 a KFold evaluation is to check the validity of the model structure. If a model
448 structure would only perform well on a few select folds, the architecture should
449 be reconsidered. It might also be due to the dataset not being representable for
450 the problem at all, yet in that case not much can be done. In this work, a KFold
451 was performed where k was equal to the amount of datapoints. This resulted in a
452 number of 132, 264 or 396 models per model subtype, depending on which type was
453 evaluated. Each fold only had a single datapoint to validate on; therefore, it can be
454 expected that the actual training will suffer from some overfitting. If the fold can
455 still be accurately predicted then, it implies a high representability of that fold for
456 the entire dataset. This type of KFold aims at visualizing how representable each
457 point is in the context of the whole dataset, along with general model applicability.
458 It serves to ensure a model architecture that works for the majority of data
459 shuffles, and helps explain deviating results in the test set for regular model training.

460 **4.5. Data Augmentation.** Data augmentation refers to the process of expanding
461 the database without actually having to generate more datapoints by the usual
462 means of data acquisition. There are a multitude of ways to perform data augmen-
463 tation, even if the methods are constrained to exclusive use in CNN architectures
464 [59]. The spatial awareness of CNNs regarding images suggests simple operations
465 such as flipping, rotating or mirroring of images as a straightforward data augmen-
466 tation approach. Those operations change the picture matrix in a manner that is
467 sufficient for being interpreted by the algorithm as a distinct datapoint while losing
468 none of the inherent features needed for the regression. While data augmentation
469 did not lead to major improvements in terms of performance, it made the training
470 process yield more consistent results for different shuffling schemes of the dataset.

471 **4.6. Normalization impact on the loss function.** The used activation func-
472 tions are a mixture of ReLu- [60] and tanh-functions [61], with the latter constricting

473 the effective prediction range to 0 and 1. To avoid the division by 0 error, those
474 values are shifted up by 1 in the final lambda layer of the basic model to allow for
475 the use of the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). However, this trick has
476 a non negligible effect on the MAPE. If one calculates the difference between the
477 shifted MAPE' and the original MAPE for a single sample, they find

$$\Delta_{\text{Error}} = \text{MAPE}' - \text{MAPE} = -1/y * \text{MAPE}' \quad (6)$$

478 with y being the unshifted target of the model, ranging between 0 and 1. So the
479 MAPE' is shifted down by a factor of $-1/y$, which causes a quite significant
480 mismatch for values of y going towards 0. The errors will generally be bigger the
481 closer the targets go to 0, which can be interpreted as an increased sensitivity of the
482 model to values close to 1. This proved beneficial in reducing the generally worse
483 performance of the models near the upper data range border. Interestingly, it did
484 not seem to worsen the model performance for values close to 0.

485 **4.7. Use of callbacks.** To help prevent overfitting and speed up the training pro-
486 cesses two different callbacks from tensorflow were used: One called model check-
487 point callback and another one called early stopping callback. The first callback was
488 set up to monitor the validation loss and save the model with the lowest recorded
489 validation loss. This sets the priority on the performance on the test set, and
490 prevents overfitting by discarding training results with better training, but worse
491 validation performance. The second callback was set to stop training if no im-
492 provement on the validation could be detected within 50 epochs of the previous
493 best result. With models training for 150 epochs a great amount of time is needed
494 for computation, especially for the KFold. This time can be cut down significantly
495 by using the early stopping callback, while still giving the model the option of
496 training over all epochs, if it helps performance.

497 **4.8. Used hyperparameters.** The first hyperparameter to be considered is the
498 regularization. Elastic Net regularization, as made popular by Zou [62], was used on
499 all convolution and dense layers, except for the dense layers right before concatena-
500 tion and final output. Elastic Net has two tunable hyperparameters corresponding
501 to the linear and squared part of the regularization function, named L1 and L2,
502 respectively. The empirically best suited values were 0.0001 for L1 and 0.001 L2.
503 Those numbers seemed to produce the best tradeoff between the generalizability of
504 the model and the training time needed to achieve good model performance. All
505 regularization was implemented as kernel regularizers.

506 Another hyperparameter was the kernel size of convolutional and maxpooling lay-
507 ers. A (5,5) kernel was used for the first convolution in each wing. All subsequent
508 convolutions and all maxpooling layers used a (3,3) kernel. The main intention
509 behind using these kernels was extracting features with a minimum amount of in-
510 formation lost, with the first convolution compressing the information slightly more.
511 This was done due to the first convolutional layer using colored images as input,
512 providing more rich information, which could be processed more quickly with a
513 slightly bigger kernel.

514 A hyperparameter of great interest was the amount of values kept at the end of
515 the individual CNN wings. A balance between enough vector components to keep
516 sufficient information for the subsequent dense layers and few enough so that the
517 extracted features from the CNN are too numerous to be meaningful was required.

518 After testing several different numbers for this purpose in a grid search approach,
519 an architecture with vectors of size 10 was selected.

520 The ratio between training and test set had to be decided on as well. Since the
521 amount of data was rather low compared to machine learning standards, a 90-10
522 split was used across the board. This provides an adequate amount of datapoints
523 for the training while a k-fold like validation scheme allowed for a relatively repre-
524 sentative test error.

525 The Adam optimizer, as first published by Kingma and Ba [63] was selected as the
526 optimizer. The pre-implemented tensorflow version with a learning rate of 0.01 was
527 used.

528 The choice of learning rate was dependent on the stability of the error during
529 training and the amount of epochs needed to reach good results. Empirical tests
530 suggested the selected learning rate to provide a good equilibrium between both
531 aspects.

532 The batch size was fixed at 8, providing reasonable training times and sufficient
533 variety per batch to achieve good results. The number of epochs varied between
534 training runs and models to produce satisfying performance.

535 5. Data Availability Statement

536 The data used to train all models presented in this study are available from
537 DOI: 10.17632/zt2j5j4v44.1. The code used to generate the results presented in
538 this study can be found at
539 <https://github.com/Galdramadhur/Perovskite-Thin-Film-Characterization>.

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560 7. Author Contributions

561 M.H., L.V. and I.K. conceived the idea. L.V. and M.S. generated the experimen-
562 tal data. M.H. and I.K. trained the ML models. A.d.C. and A.G. supervised the
563 work. M.H., L.V., I.K. contributed equally in the writing and critical discussion of
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565 8. Competing Interests

566 The authors declare no competing interests.

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